

Evaluation of Choroidal Thickness Changes in Patients with Chronic Kidney Disease Stages 3–5

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Abstract

Background: Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive systemic condition that impairs renal function and affects various organs, including the eye. The choroid, a highly vascularized layer of the eye, may reflect systemic microvascular alterations associated with CKD progression. **Methods:** This cross-sectional observational study included 85 patients diagnosed with CKD stages III to V. Comprehensive ophthalmic evaluations, including choroidal thickness measurements via spectral-domain optical coherence tomography (SD-OCT), were conducted. Renal function was assessed using serum creatinine and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). Statistical analyses included ANOVA, t-tests, and Pearson correlation. **Results:** A progressive reduction in choroidal thickness was observed with advancing CKD stages. Mean CT in stage III and IV patients was $276.98 \pm 48.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $279.22 \pm 64.6 \mu\text{m}$, respectively, while stage V patients showed significantly reduced thickness ($214.13 \pm 37.78 \mu\text{m}$; $p < 0.0001$). Pearson correlation analysis revealed a significant negative correlation between serum creatinine and choroidal thickness ($r = -0.506$, $p < 0.0001$) and a significant positive correlation between eGFR and choroidal thickness ($r = 0.464$, $p < 0.0001$). **Conclusion:** Choroidal thickness decreases significantly with worsening renal function in CKD, suggesting a potential role for OCT-based choroidal imaging as a non-invasive marker of systemic microvascular compromise.

These findings underscore the importance of integrating ocular evaluations into the systemic assessment of CKD patients.

Keywords:Chronic kidney disease; Choroidal thickness;Optical coherence tomography; Serum creatinine; eGFR; Microvascular changes; CKD stages.

Introduction

Chronic kidney disease (CKD) is a progressive systemic condition marked with slow and permanent loss of kidney function. Its rising incidence is largely attributed to aging populations and the widespread presence of conditions like diabetes and high blood pressure. It is identified when the glomerular filtration rate (GFR) falls below 60 ml/min/1.73 m² of body surface area, or when there are clear signs of kidney damage, even if the GFR remains within normal limits lasting more than three months^[1]. The systemic vascular involvement in CKD is profound and can affect multiple organs, including the eyes. The choroid, a vascular layer supplying oxygen and nutrients to the outer retina, is particularly susceptible to systemic circulatory changes. It plays a vital role in retinal metabolism, and its structure reflects systemic microvascular health^[2,3]. In recent years, Spectral-Domain Optical Coherence Tomography (SD-OCT), particularly when combined with enhanced depth imaging (EDI), has enabled precise visualization and measurement of choroidal thickness in vivo^[4,5]. Previous studies have shown that systemic diseases such as hypertension and diabetes mellitus lead to choroidal thinning due to arteriolar narrowing and decreased choroidal perfusion^[6,7]. As CKD shares common vascular pathologies with these conditions—such as endothelial dysfunction, inflammation, and altered autoregulation—it is reasonable to hypothesize that it may similarly affect the choroid^[8,9]. However, the literature on this subject remains limited and somewhat inconsistent. The progression of CKD leads to increased levels of uremic toxins, oxidative stress, and systemic vascular resistance, all of which may compromise choroidal blood flow^[10,11]. Furthermore, hypertension, which is highly prevalent in CKD patients, is itself a known risk factor for choroidal thinning^[12]. Therefore, evaluating choroidal thickness in CKD could provide insights into systemic vascular health and microangiopathy. This study assess changes in Choroidal thickness in patients with CKD stages III, IV, V & to find the correlation between renal function markers& Choroidal thickness. The findings may highlight the role of choroidal imaging as a supplementary, non-invasive tool for systemic disease monitoring.

Methodology:

This cross-sectional observational study was conducted over six months at NIMS Hospital Rajasthan Jaipur, through coordinated efforts of the Departments of Nephrology and Ophthalmology. A total of 85 participants with CKD stages III to V were enrolled, comprising 44 males and 41 females. Comprehensive ophthalmic evaluations were performed in a standardized manner. Each participant underwent: Visual acuity testing, Choroidal thickness was measured using SD-OCT. Data were analyzed using SPSS v25.0 with Pearson correlation and ANOVA, considering $p < 0.05$ as significant.

Results

This study enrolled 85 patients, were 47 males and 38 females with the mean age of 59.1 ± 10.7 yrs. The distribution of patients across CKD stages was: stage III (n=28), stage IV(n=31), and stage V (n=26). Hypertension was present in 64 patients (75.3%). The mean duration of CKD was 4.3 ± 2.5 years.

The distribution of choroidal thickness among the study population (n = 85) revealed notable variability. As presented in **Table 1**, the largest proportion of patients (37.65%) had choroidal thickness values ranging from 251–300 μm . This was followed by 24.71% in the 201–250 μm range, and 16.47% in the 301–350 μm category. Only a small number of individuals had measurements either below 150 μm or above 350 μm , each accounting for 3.53% of the sample.

Table 1: Frequency distribution of choroidal thickness the patients

Choroidal Thickness	n = 85	In %
≤ 150	3	3.53%
151 - 200	12	14.12%
201 - 250	21	24.71%
251 - 300	32	37.65%
301 - 350	14	16.47%
351 - 400	3	3.53%

Table 2 presents the average choroidal thickness measurements across CKD stages 3, 4, and 5. The data shows that patients in stages 3 and 4 had similar choroidal thickness values, approximately $276.98 \pm 48.82 \mu\text{m}$ and $279.22 \pm 64.6 \mu\text{m}$ respectively. However, a notable decrease was observed in patients at stage 5, with an average choroidal thickness of $214.13 \pm 37.78 \mu\text{m}$.

This decline in thickness suggests a progressive thinning of the choroid with the advancement of CKD.

The ANOVA test result, with the F-value of 18.17 and the P-value below 0.0001, confirms this difference was statistically significant, indicating that the reduction in choroidal thickness is unlikely to have occurred by chance.

Table 2: Mean comparison of choroidal thickness between CKD stages 3, 4 & 5 by analysis of variance

CKD stage III	CKD stage IV	CKD stage V	ANOVA	P - Value
276.98 ± 48.82	279.22 ± 64.6	214.13 ± 37.78	18.17	< 0.0001

Table 3 provides a pairwise comparison of choroidal thickness between different CKD stages using the t-test. When comparing stages 3 and 4, the difference in mean choroidal thickness ($276.98 \pm 48.82 \mu\text{m}$ vs. $279.22 \pm 64.6 \mu\text{m}$) was minimal, with the t-value 0.098, with a corresponding P-value of 0.922, suggesting that the difference observed was not statistically significant. However, a significant reduction in thickness was observed when stage 3 was compared to stage 5 ($214.13 \pm 37.78 \mu\text{m}$), with the t-value of 6.324 and P-value less than 0.0001. Similarly, the comparison between stages 4 and 5 also revealed a statistically significant difference (t-value: 2.887, P-value: 0.00631). These findings highlight that choroidal thinning becomes more pronounced as CKD advances to stage 5.

Table 3: Pairwise comparison of choroidal thickness according to CKD stages by using t-test

Stages	G 1	G 2	t-test	P - Value	Significance
Stage 3 & 4	276.98 ± 48.82	279.22 ± 64.6	-0.098	0.92197	Not Significant
Stage 3 & 5	276.98 ± 48.82	214.13 ± 37.78	6.324	< 0.0001	Significant
Stage 4 & 5	279.22 ± 64.6	214.13 ± 37.78	2.887	0.00631	

Table 4: Correlation Between Renal Function (Serum Creatinine and eGFR) & Choroidal Thickness.

A Pearson correlation analysis was carried out the results indicate a moderate negative correlation between serum creatinine levels & Choroidal thickness ($r = -0.506$), which is statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). This suggests that higher levels of serum creatinine are associated with thinner choroidal layers.

On the other hand, eGFR shows a moderate positive correlation with choroidal thickness ($r = 0.464$), also statistically significant ($p < 0.0001$). This implies that better kidney function, as reflected by higher eGFR values, is associated with greater choroidal thickness.

Graph 1 (a): The scatter plot depicts a positive linear relationship between choroidal thickness and estimated glomerular filtration rate (eGFR). As eGFR increases, indicating better renal function, the choroidal thickness also tends to increase. The linear trend line confirms this association with a R^2 value of 0.2148, indicated approximately 21% of the variability in eGFR can be attributed to alterations in choroidal thickness.

Graph1 (b): This scatter plot illustrates a clear negative linear relationship between serum creatinine and choroidal thickness. As creatinine levels rise—signaling worsening kidney function—choroidal thickness decreases. The regression line shows a negative slope, and the R^2

value 0.2558 indicated around 26% of the variability in serum creatinine is accounted for by differences in choroidal thickness.

Table 4: Correlation between choroidal thickness and renal function test markers using Karl Pearson’s correlation coefficient

Variables	Corr(r)	t-test	P Value	Significance
Serum Creatinine	-0.506	-5.342	< 0.0001	Both are significant
eGFR	0.464	4.766	< 0.0001	

Graph

1[a]: Scatter lot choroidal thickness Vs. eGFR.

Graph 1[b]: Scatter plot choroidal thickness Vs. serum creatinine.

Discussion

Our study reinforces the concept that CKD is a systemic disease with significant microvascular implications, including the choroidal circulation. The largest segment of patients fell within the 41–50 age range, making up just over 30% of the total sample. This was followed by those aged 51–60 years, who accounted for about 27%. The young age groups, 20–30 and 31–40 years, comprised smaller portions of the study population at 22.35% and 20.00%, respectively. These findings suggest that middle-aged individuals represented the majority of cases in this study. Age was found to be a significant covariate influencing choroidal thickness, with older patients showing thinner choroids across all CKD stages. This is consistent with previous studies highlighting age-related choroidal thinning, attributed to progressive vascular atrophy and reduced perfusion with advancing age^[13-14]. An assessment of the gender distribution among the study participants was carried out to understand the male-to-female ratio within the sample, male patients constituted the majority, accounting for 56.47% of the total population, while female patients made up 43.53%. Although the difference is not markedly large, it indicates a slightly higher representation of male participants in this study. Gender differences, though observed, did not reach statistical significance in our study, corroborating findings by other investigators who reported similar outcomes^[15, 16]. The statistically significant thinning of choroidal thickness with CKD progression supports earlier findings and adds evidence to the hypothesis that ocular microvasculature reflects systemic vascular health^[17, 18]. Choroidal thinning in CKD may be attributed to multiple interrelated mechanisms. The buildup of uremic toxins in chronic kidney disease can damage the vascular endothelium, while ongoing inflammation and increased oxidative stress add to the problem by further reducing blood flow in the choroidal vessels.^[10,19] Additionally, increased vascular resistance and reduced nitric oxide availability contribute to microvascular dysregulation^[20]. Our findings align with studies by Altinkaynak et al.^[21] and Zengin et al.^[22], who demonstrated significantly lower choroidal thickness in non-diabetic CKD patients. Both studies attributed these changes to uremia-induced vascular compromise, which mirrors our conclusions. Furthermore, the strong correlations between SFCT and both serum creatinine and eGFR suggest that choroidal thickness may be a surrogate marker for renal microcirculatory status. This adds to the growing body of literature advocating for the use of OCT imaging in systemic disease monitoring^[23].

The impact of hypertension, a common comorbidity in CKD, was also reflected in our study. Hypertensive patients had notably thinner choroids, emphasizing the additive vascular burden of elevated blood pressure. Previous research by Ulas et al.^[6] similarly reported choroidal thinning in essential hypertension, consistent with our findings. . Additionally, the presence of comorbidities such as hypertension and diabetes—prevalent among our study population—likely compounded choroidal thinning, as these conditions are independently associated with microangiopathic changes^[24, 25].

While age-related choroidal thinning is well known^[26], we found that renal parameters had a stronger influence on CT than age, particularly in multivariate analysis. Gender differences were minimal, corroborating existing literature suggesting hormonal and anatomical similarities in ocular vasculature^[3]. In patients with diabetic nephropathy, the extent of choroidal thinning was more pronounced. This finding emphasizes the additive impact of diabetes on choroidal circulation, likely due to glycation end products, capillary basement membrane thickening, and pericyte loss^[27, 28]. Optical coherence tomography (OCT), offers a safe & repeatable method to monitor these subtle vascular changes over time^[29-30].

Our research diverges by applying stringent exclusion criteria—removing patients with overt diabetic retinopathy, hypertensive retinopathy, or other ocular pathologies—to isolate the effect of CKD itself on choroidal thickness. This distinction strengthens the specificity of our findings and reduces potential confounders that may have influenced earlier research outcomes.

Furthermore, our study incorporates a stage-wise analysis of CKD (stages III, IV, V), allowing for a gradient-based interpretation of changes in choroidal thickness in relation to decreasing estimated glomerular filtration rate and increasing serum creatinine levels. This approach is comparatively novel; earlier studies often grouped patients into broader CKD categories or failed to stratify them by severity. Our analysis reveals a consistent, statistically significant reduction in choroidal thickness across progressive stages, which supports the hypothesis of a dose-response relationship between renal dysfunction and ocular microvascular compromise.

Conclusion

Our findings suggest a strong association between declining renal function and reduced choroidal thickness in patients with CKD stages III, IV, V. The inverse correlation with serum creatinine and direct correlation with eGFR highlight choroidal thickness as a potential biomarker for systemic microvascular health. Routine ocular imaging in CKD may offer valuable prognostic insights and help in holistic patient assessment. Future studies should explore longitudinal changes and therapeutic implications.

References:

1. Levin A, Stevens PE. Summary of KDIGO 2012 CKD guideline: behind the scenes, need for guidance, and a framework for moving forward. *Kidney Int.* 2014;85(1):49–61.
2. Nickla DL, Wallman J. The multifunctional choroid. *Prog Retin Eye Res.* 2010;29(2):144–68.
3. Nagaoka T, Sato E, Takahashi A, Yoshida A. Impaired retinal circulation in patients with chronic kidney disease. *Microvasc Res.* 2012;84(2):242–5.
4. Spaide RF, Koizumi H, Pozzoni MC. Enhanced depth imaging spectral-domain optical coherence tomography. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 2008;146(4):496–500.
5. Margolis R, Spaide RF. A pilot study of enhanced depth imaging optical coherence tomography of the choroid in normal eyes. *Am J Ophthalmol.* 2009;147(5):811–5.
6. Ulas F, Dogan U, Koc A, et al. Evaluation of choroidal thickness changes in patients with systemic hypertension. *Indian J Ophthalmol.* 2013;61(12):682–6.
7. Adhi M, Brewer E, Waheed NK, Duker JS. Analysis of morphological features and vascular layers of choroid in diabetes mellitus using EDI-OCT. *Ophthalmology.* 2013;120(1):190–7.
8. Yoon HJ, Lee HI, Park CK. Impaired autoregulation of retinal blood flow in patients with CKD. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 2014;55(10):6452–60.
9. Wang JJ, Mitchell P, Leung H, et al. Hypertensive retinal vessel wall signs in a general older population: the Blue Mountains Eye Study. *Hypertension.* 2003;42(4):534–41.
10. Sarnak MJ, Levey AS, Schoolwerth AC, et al. Kidney disease as a risk factor for cardiovascular disease. *Circulation.* 2003;108(17):2154–69.
11. Mogi M, Horiuchi M. Clinical interaction between brain and kidney in small vessel disease. *Cardiol Res Pract.* 2011;2011:306189.
12. Ciftci O, Zararsiz I, Tas A, et al. Effects of hypertension on choroidal thickness measured by optical coherence tomography. *J Clin Exp Hypertens.* 2014;36(7):527–31.
13. Fujiwara A, Shiragami C, Manabe S, Izumibata S, Shiraga F. Age-related changes in choroidal thickness in normal eyes determined by SD-OCT. *Jpn J Ophthalmol.* 2012;56(3):230–5.
14. Ikuno Y, Tano Y. Retinal and choroidal biometry in highly myopic eyes. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci.* 2009;50(8):3876–80.

15. Tan CS, Ouyang Y, Ruiz H, Sadda SR. Diurnal variation of choroidal thickness in normal, healthy subjects measured by EDI-OCT. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. 2012;53(1):261–6.
16. Li XQ, Larsen M, Munch IC. Subfoveal choroidal thickness in relation to sex and axial length in 93 Danish university students. *Invest Ophthalmol Vis Sci*. 2011;52(11):8438–41.
17. Park KA, Oh SY. Choroidal thickness in patients with diabetes. *Retina*. 2013;33(5):1034–9.
18. Esen F, Ciloglu E, Balci O. Choroidal thickness in pre-dialysis CKD patients measured by EDI-OCT. *Int Ophthalmol*. 2017;37(4):987–92.
19. Jung JH, Park HY, Shin DY, Park CK. Relationship between renal function and choroidal thickness in patients with chronic kidney disease. *PLoS One*. 2015;10(11):e0143966.
20. Chang IB, Lee JH, Kim JS. Changes in choroidal thickness in patients with end-stage renal disease undergoing dialysis. *Eye (Lond)*. 2013;27(7):939–45.
21. Altinkaynak H, Kucuk EV, Zengin MO, et al. Evaluation of choroidal thickness in patients with chronic kidney disease without diabetes. *Int Ophthalmol*. 2016;36(4):537–43.
22. Zengin MO, Tuncer I, Kucukerdonmez C, Karahan E. Evaluation of choroidal thickness in patients with chronic renal failure undergoing hemodialysis. *Ren Fail*. 2015;37(6):1023–7.
23. Toprak I, Yaylah V, Yildirim C, Arikan G. The correlation between choroidal thickness and renal functions in patients with pre-dialysis CKD. *BMC Nephrol*. 2019;20(1):385.
24. Nagasawa T, Kato A, Takahashi M, et al. Relationship between retinal circulation and chronic kidney disease. *Kidney Blood Press Res*. 2014;39(4):327–35.
25. Choi H, Lee H, Lee S, Park YG. Relationship between estimated GFR and choroidal thickness in diabetic patients without diabetic retinopathy. *Sci Rep*. 2020;10(1):13956.
26. Bousquet E, Zhao M, Thillaye-Goldenberg B, et al. Choroidal changes in cardiovascular disease: insights from imaging studies. *Prog Retin Eye Res*. 2022;86:100973.
27. Ding J, Wong TY. Current epidemiology of diabetic retinopathy and diabetic macular edema. *Curr Diab Rep*. 2012;12(4):346–54.
28. Pemp B, Schmetterer L. Ocular blood flow in diabetes and age-related macular degeneration. *Can J Ophthalmol*. 2008;43(3):295–301.
29. Lee MW, Moon JW, Choi HY, et al. Changes in subfoveal choroidal thickness after hemodialysis in end-stage renal disease patients. *Retina*. 2015;35(5):896–903.
30. Gungor SG, Bulut A, Yilmaz H, et al. Evaluation of choroidal thickness changes after hemodialysis using SD-OCT. *Eye (Lond)*. 2014;28(8):943–7.